

Notes on the red beetle jumping spider *Pachyballus castaneus* Simon, 1900 in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae)

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ABSTRACT: Information on the rare red beetle jumping spider *Pachyballus castaneus* Simon, 1900 is provided. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), the species was recollected and photographed. The general morphology, behaviour, conservation status and distribution of the species are discussed along with images of live specimens.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome, KwaZulu-Natal, mimicry, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Pachyballus* Simon, 1900 is known from nine species, of which eight are recorded from Africa and one from New Caledonia (World Spider Catalog, 2022). Some species of these small spiders possibly mimic beetles.

Pachyballus castaneus Simon, 1900 was originally described from a single female housed in the National Museum of Natural History in Paris, France. The type locality was only given as Natal (South Africa). In a revision of *Pachyballus* by Wesolowska *et al.* (2020), they were unable to locate the type and they designated a neotype from the Ophathe Game Reserve, KwaZulu-Natal, to stabilise the nomenclature. They redescribed the female and described the male as the original species description was lacking detail.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), the species was recollected and photographed. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status are provided.

METHODS

During SANSa surveys, specimens were sampled from different areas in the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Voucher specimens of the species are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria and the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

TAXONOMY

Pachyballus castaneus Simon, 1900

Pachyballus castaneus Simon, 1900: 400 (female); Wesolowska, Azarkina & Wiśniewski, 2020: 55: 6, 18–28, 129 (male, female).

Diagnostic characteristics: Small (2.5–3.00 mm length), robust spiders, with strongly flattened bodies covered with a very hard, sclerotised exoskeleton (Fig. 1); dorsum of their body has a characteristic pitted micro sculpture with short scattered pale setae (Fig. 2). Carapace reddish brown to dark brown in male (Fig. 3); eye field covers more or less half of carapace, vicinity of eyes black; white setae present around eye region (Fig. 1); posterior edge of carapace covered by abdomen. Abdomen dark reddish brown, rounded to heart shaped, as wide as long; dorsum totally covered with strongly sclerotised scutum (Figs 4–5); venter with two scuta (Fig. 7). Legs short with first pair larger than others (Figs 2–3) with femora thickened and the tibiae ventrally with dense setae. Juveniles resemble adults but more reddish (Fig. 6). Epigyne is horseshoe shaped (Figs 7–9) and palp with short embolus (Fig. 10).

Figs 1–3. *Pachyballus castaneus*: 1. Female anterior view (Photo: Vida van der Walt). 2. Female lateral view (Photo: Bruce Blake). 3. Male anterior view (Photo: Bruce Blake).

Figs 4–6. *Pachyballus castaneus*: 4. Female anterior view. 5. Female dorsal view. 6. Juvenile. Photos: Vida vd Walt

Figs 7–10. *Pachyballus castaneus*: 7. Female ventral view. 8. Epigyne (Photos: Vida van der Walt). 9–10. Epigyne and palp after Wesolowska *et al.* (2020).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa, Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Ulundi, Ophathe Game Reserve (28°23'S, 31°24'E), (NCA 2008/4147; NCA 2008/4140; NCA 2008/4167; NCA 2008/4154; NCA 2008/3993; NCA 2008/3971); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Crocodile Centre (28°21'S, 32°25'E), (NCA 2012/5736); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (28°23'S, 32°25'E), (NCA 2012/4019; NCA 2012/5737); iSimangaliso Wetland Park Lake St. Lucia, Fannies Island (28°06'S, 32°27'E), (NMBA 08069); uMkuze, Banghoek Lodge (27°45'S, 32°08'E), (NCA 2012/3965); Ndumo Game Reserve (26°55'S, 32°19'E), (NCA 2009/3660); Si-hangwane, Tembe Elephant Park, 40 km from Kosi Bay (27°02'S, 32°25'E), (NCA 94/828; NCA 2008/505); Hellsgate (28°00'S, 32°48'E), (NCA 2010/155; NCA 2010/156); Kloof (-29° 46'S, 30° 49' E) (photographs); Umhlanga (-29.737'S, 31°4'25.1"E) (photographs).
Mpumalanga: Mbombela, Agricultural College (25°27'S, 30°59'E), (NCA 2000/223); Wildlife College, 10 km from Orpen Gate of Kruger National Park (24°28'S, 31°23'E), (NCA 2003/626).
Limpopo: Little Leigh (22°56'S, 29°22'E), (NCA 2009/2232).

HABITAT

The species was sampled by beating and fogging vegetation in the Savannah (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biomes. They were sampled while beating overgrazed savannah and dense bush thicket at Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015) and vegetation in *Vachellia xanthophloea* forests at Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006). At several localities in the iSimangaliso Wetland Park, they were mainly collected during canopy fogging of *Breonadia salicina*, *Trichilia dregeana*, *V. karroo* and *Euclea divinorum*. The Mbombela specimen was collected while beating citrus trees (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

BEHAVIOUR

The second author regularly found this species in his garden at Kloof. They usually wandered around on broadleaved plants during the daytime. Two very similar, small beetle spp. (Figs 13–14) (family Coccinellidae, possibly *Exochomus* sp.) were present on the same plants the *Pachyballus* were found. The morphological similarities between the mimic and its potential models lie in the presence of white setae covering the spider's body (Fig. 11), together with a series of tufts of long, erect, white setae on the carapace, abdomen and legs.

Figs 11–12. Coccinellidae (possibly *Exochomus* sp.). (Photos: Bruce Blake). 13–14. *Pachyballus castaneus* showing resemblance to the Coccinellidae. (Photos: Peter Webb).

They fed on a variety of insects and preyed on both nymphs and adults of booklice/barklice (order Psocoptera), jumping plant lice (family Psyllidae) and midges (family Chironomidae) (Figs 15–17). In captivity, they had a voracious appetite and readily fed on small *Drosophila melanogaster* flies. Walking was their primary means of locomotion and they only jumped when necessary to cross a void and ran very fast when they were disturbed.

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Figs 15–17. *Pachyballus castaneus* feeding on book louse (Order: Psocoptera), jumping plant lice (family Psyllidae) and Diptera midges (family: Chironomidae). (Photos: Bruce Blake)

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: A review Arachnida Araneae. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders Arachnida Araneae of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2015. Diversity of non-acarine arachnids of the Ophathe Game Reserve, South Africa: Testing a rapid sampling protocol. *Koedoe* 57(1): Art. #1255, 15 pp. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v57i1.1255>.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WESOŁOWSKA W. 2006. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the Ndumo Game Reserve, Maputoland, South Africa. *Koedoe* 49: 1–22.
- SIMON E. 1900. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux de la famille des Attidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 44: 381–407.
- WESOŁOWSKA W., AZARKINA G.N. & WIŚNIEWSKI K. 2020. A revision of *Pachyballus* Simon, 1900 and *Peplometus* Simon, 1900 (Araneae, Salticidae, Ballini) with descriptions of new species. *ZooKeys* 944: 47–98. doi:10.3897/zookeys.944.49921
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2022. World Spider Catalog. Version 23.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 10 February 2022. doi: 10.24436/2